

THE PRACTICE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN ON ENSURING GENDER EQUALITY

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Abstract: In this article, the reforms carried out to ensure gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the path taken, the programs of mutual cooperation with international organizations and the work carried out based on them will be highlighted. In addition, the legislation of Uzbekistan is analyzed and the conditions and privileges given to women are shown.

Keywords: gender, gender equality, women's rights, reforms, benefits, conditions.

Аннотация: В данной статье будут освещены реформы, проводимые по обеспечению гендерного равенства в Республике Узбекистан, пройденный путь, программы взаимного сотрудничества с международными организациями и проводимая на их основе работа. Кроме того, проанализировано законодательство Узбекистана и показаны условия и привилегии, предоставляемые женщинам.

Ключевые слова: гендер, гендерное равенство, права женщин, реформы, льготы, условия.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida gender tengligini ta'minlash borasida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar, bosib o'tgan yo'l, xalqaro tashkilotlar bilan o'zaro hamkorlik dasturlari va ular asosida amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar yoritib beriladi. Shuningdek, O'zbekiston qonunchiligi tahlil qilinib, xotin-qizlarga berilayotgan shart-sharoit va imtiyozlar ko'rsatildi.

Kalit so'zlar: gender, gender tengligi, ayollar huquqlari, islohotlar, imtiyozlar, shart-sharoitlar.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, more attention is being paid to ensuring gender equality than ever before. Protection of women's rights and their comprehensive support has become one of the most urgent issues.

In accordance with the United Nations (UN) General Assembly Resolution No. 70 adopted at the Summit on Sustainable Development in September 2015, as well as the consistent implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals of the

UN Global Agenda until 2030. The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a Resolution "On measures to implement national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development until 2030" in order to organize systematic work on

At the same time, within the framework of the implementation of the Fifth Sustainable Development Goal, Uzbekistan has developed nine tasks related to "Ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of all women".

In accordance with the objectives of the fifth goal (Gender equality), by 2030, eliminate all forms of discrimination against all women, promote the full and effective participation of women and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and social life. It is necessary to provide. In addition, this goal includes the implementation of gender equality principles in the process of adoption of State programs at different levels of the state.

In recent years, efforts to ensure gender equality and increase the role of women in social and political life have been carried out in several directions:

- ✓ improvement of legislation on women's rights;
- ✓ improvement of the institutional framework for the protection of women;
- ✓ raising public awareness of gender equality and women's rights;
- ✓ training of responsible officials on the basis of relevant legal norms to ensure their compliance in law enforcement practice.

In Uzbekistan, a number of legal documents, including presidential decrees and decisions on ensuring women's rights, in particular, on gender equality and protecting women from violence and oppression, strengthening the status of women's entrepreneurship development, have been adopted.

In terms of introducing gender equality, it is necessary to emphasize the positive developments in education. That is, since 2017, the activity of part-time departments in various specialties has been restored in most higher educational institutions. This form of education allows young women to obtain higher education without compromising childcare and other family responsibilities.

Taking this opportunity, I consider it appropriate to quote President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis in June 2019:

"I am worried about the stereotype that has appeared in the minds of our people. Usually we respect a woman first of all as a mother, a guardian of the family fortress. This is certainly true. But today, every woman should not be an ordinary

observer, but also an active and proactive participant in the democratic changes taking place in the country."

On this day, at the invitation of the President, for the first time in the history of the country, a woman - Tanzila Norboeva - was elected as the chairman of the Senate. It is known that Norboeva worked as the Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Chairman of the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan.

As for the legislative measures in this area, in order to further improve the legal basis for ensuring and protecting women's rights in Uzbekistan, in September 2019, "Guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men are correct" on" and "On protection of women from harassment and violence" Laws were adopted. Almost all UN agencies, including the United Nations Development Program, the United Nations Population Fund, the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, and the International Organization for Migration have adopted these two laws. gave their comments and suggestions.

As for the institutional measures on gender equality, at the same time, within the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the new Women and Girls, who are engaged in harmonizing international standards in the national legislation on ensuring women's rights and eliminating any form of discrimination, and a gender equality committee was established. In addition, in order to further strengthen the guarantees and support of labor rights, to help victims of domestic violence, the rehabilitation and adaptation of victims of violence and suicide prevention republican center and Khatin -new structures such as the Center for Girls' Entrepreneurship, the Scientific and Practical Research Center "Family" under the Government were established.

It is important that all these newly established institutional mechanisms, together with the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan, become a single integrated mechanism for women's rights, gender equality and elimination of discrimination against women in accordance with the UN Convention.

It should be noted that the adopted regulatory documents and practical measures are an important step in the field of gender policy of Uzbekistan, and it fully complies with the international norms and standards of legislation and practice, at the same time, some of them Based on the recommendations of UN human rights agencies.

The adoption of the Law "On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence" was especially important. This Law was adopted after many years of discussions. The law is the basis for the protection of women by providing assistance to victims of domestic violence, providing them with shelters, hotlines, and mandatory prosecution for not only physical violence, but also psychological or economic crimes. Such measures have long been recommended, in particular, by UN human rights agencies.

In the field of monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of gender policy, significant changes have taken place on the site www.gender.stat.uz by introducing additional 54 gender indicators.

At the same time, it is necessary to carry out continuous consistent work in this direction. Here, not only the accepted instructions, but also their compliance with international obligations and standards, timely and accurate implementation on the ground are of great importance.

In this sense, it is necessary to consistently continue the work to ensure the full and effective participation of women at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and social life.

Therefore, to ensure the implementation of the Laws "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" and "On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence" maps" is planned to be accepted. There is also a plan to adopt a national strategy for gender equality. UN agencies are ready to continue to support gender equality and non-discrimination issues, including the planning, development and implementation of special instruments, and the development of special provisions of new codes - criminal, procedural and executive phases.

Also, it is important to ensure that gender analysis of the legislation is mandatory in order to ensure that the adopted documents of one or another level are the same for women and men.

In turn, in addition to business incubators, it is necessary to take measures to encourage women in the field of education and science, as well as to attract them to the field of natural and technical sciences by creating STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) laboratories. This, in turn, helps increase women's employment and competitiveness in the modern labor market.

The measures taken should cover all regions of the country and all categories of women. In particular, the consistent implementation of the Sustainable

Development Goals of the UN Global Agenda until 2030, taking into account the principles of the agenda, especially the principle of "leaving no one behind", with particular attention to the situation of women and girls who are prone to various forms of discrimination. focus is a pressing issue. Here, women from rural areas in remote areas of the country, ethnic minority groups, women with disabilities, women with HIV/AIDS, women in places of deprivation of liberty and restrictions (including prisons, boarding houses, nursing homes and psychiatric hospitals), human rights defenders, focusing on stateless persons and refugees.

Currently, within the framework of cooperation between UN agencies in Uzbekistan, a special group on gender issues has been established, which includes representatives of almost all UN agencies. For example, the recommendations for Laws mentioned above were still part of the group's work during the project. UN agencies are always ready to assist in the development of other legal documents, such as the work of this group.

In addition, many activities on raising awareness of women's problems in various formats, such as a conference, a video, a legal clinic under the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan, and social networks are on the agenda. In this regard, the Center for Development Strategy and other non-governmental organizations are actively working together.

In turn, the UN team in Uzbekistan provides comprehensive support to the country to ensure gender equality within the framework of the "Sustainable Development Cooperation Program for 2021-2025", which is currently being developed with extensive consultations of all national partners and other stakeholders. is being shown.

In the Resolution of the Senate of the Supreme Assembly of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 28, 2021 No. SQ-297-IV "On approval of the strategy for achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" for women and men in the last four years large-scale reforms aimed at achieving equal rights and opportunities, ensuring their equal participation in the management of society and state affairs, social and legal support for women, as well as protection of women from oppression and violence done.

The issue of gender equality has been raised to the level of state policy, and 25 legislative documents related to the field have been adopted.

The commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan on issues of ensuring gender equality, the committee on issues of women and girls and gender equality was established in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

For the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, the number of women in the parliament has reached a level consistent with the recommendations set by the UN, the number of women in the parliament has reached 32%, and it has risen to the 37th place among 190 parliaments in the world.

The share of women in management positions reached 27%, in parties 44%, in higher education 40%, in entrepreneurship 35%.

In order to provide socio-economic support to women and to work with them individually, the "Women's register" system was introduced, and 300 billion soums were allocated annually from the state budget.

The system of covering the tuition fees of needy girls who have lost their parents or one of them, single women without a breadwinner was introduced, and the number of grants for girls from needy families for admission to higher education institutions was doubled.

In order to develop women's entrepreneurship, preferential loans in the amount of 6.9 trillion soums were allocated to more than 224 thousand women.

The reforms carried out in the field have a positive effect on the place of our country in international rankings, and in the Women, Business and Law Index of the World Bank, Uzbekistan is among the 27 countries that have implemented significant reforms in terms of women's rights and gender equality in 2020. was included in the list and increased by 5 places and took the 134th place among 190 countries.

Uzbekistan has always shown that it is committed to the goals and principles of the UN Charter and other universally recognized norms of international law.

At the UN General Assembly Summit on Sustainable Development held in September 2015, Resolution No. 70 was adopted, and 125 target tasks and 206 indicators were developed to achieve 16 national goals considered urgent for our country.

In particular, the 5th goal in the field of sustainable development - Ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of all women is in sync with the reforms aimed at ensuring equal rights and opportunities of women and men in our country.

As a result of comprehensive reforms carried out in recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has a strong legal framework for ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men in all spheres of public life and activity, and protecting women from oppression and violence. the foundations have been laid.

In particular, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" was adopted.

More than 1,300 women are working in the system of state and public organizations, including 45 women in ministries and departments, 39 women in the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers, and 207 women in local government bodies.

About 50 percent of the 21,435,000 registered voters or 10,825 641 are women.

41 percent of the candidates nominated in these elections are women, and their number has increased from the 30 percent quota set by the Election Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Women make up 32 percent of the deputies of the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 25 percent of the members of the Senate, the Dzhokorgi Council of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, and local councils.

The issue of ensuring gender equality has risen to the level of state policy, and in the upper house of the parliament, the Committee on Women and Gender Equality, the Commission on Ensuring Gender Equality of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Equal Rights for Women and Men and advisory councils on issues of provision of opportunities, Republican Women's Public Council were established.

For the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, the number of women in the national parliament reached the level corresponding to the recommendations of the United Nations. The parliament of our country has risen to the 37th place among 190 national parliaments in the world in terms of the number of women.

Also, 49% of the members of the Democratic Party of Uzbekistan "National Revival" and the People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan, 46% of the members of the Social-Democratic Party of Uzbekistan "Adolat", "Liberal-Democratic Party of Uzbekistan" and 41% of the members of "Uzbekistan Ecological Party" are women.

The socio-economic policy carried out in Uzbekistan at all stages of reforms includes wide-ranging issues. Additional guarantees were given regarding the systematic increase of the population's income, the formation of employment and

labor relations, the social protection and support of certain categories of the population, including women entrepreneurs and farmers.

In particular, in order to ensure the employment of women, to widely involve them in business activities, the practice of allocating preferential loans was launched.

More than 30% of the clients of the microcredit base of commercial banks are women. Loans in the amount of 4.9 trillion soums were allocated to more than 172 thousand women at the expense of commercial banks. As a result, the number of women who started business increased by 45,000 in one year.

Starting from 2019, a system of providing employment to the population and creating new jobs on the basis of the state order was established. The procedure for issuing temporary work permits to self-employed citizens and recording their work experience has been introduced. As a result, the share of women employed in the informal sector reached 27%.

REFERENCES

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
2. United Nations (UN) General Assembly Resolution No. 70 adopted at the September 2015 Summit on Sustainable Development.
3. Resolution of the Senate of the Supreme Assembly of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 28, 2021 No. SQ-297-IV "On approval of the strategy for achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030".
4. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. ORQ-562 "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" adopted on September 2, 2019.

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